

Murayghan: Monumental Sabaic inscription of King Abraha's raid against Mecca in the Quranic "Year of the Elephant" (c. 552 AD) (Ry 506)

Pre-Islamic military expeditions in the Hejaz

Murayghan:
Graffiti of Abraha's cavaliers and warriors

Pre-islamitische
militaire
expedities in de
Hejaz:
de rotsinscripties
in Murayghan

Expéditions
militaires
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dans la région du
Hejaz :
les inscriptions
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